

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking System on Unemployment among Youths in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria

Olayiwola, Aanuoluwa Oladiran

Email: connectaanuoluwaolayiwola@gmail.com

Tel: +234 703 329 7403

Department of Business Education, Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo

Abstract

This study examined the impact of beyond-the-branch banking system on unemployment among youths in Oyo East Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 995 beyond-the-branch bankers and 285 respondents were selected using simple random sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection and it was validated by two Business Education experts. Pilot study was conducted and the data collected therefrom were tested using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test, 0.677 reliability level was obtained. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that beyond-the-branch banking afforded the youth the opportunity to make regular profits, have a stable source of income and save money to set up other businesses. It was also revealed that the major challenges incapacitating young Nigerians from making the most of these opportunities include but not limited to shortage of working capital and security risks. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should facilitate loans specifically for youths venturing into the beyond-the-branch banking so as to provide them with sufficient working capital. Banks and other financial institutions, as a form of Corporate Social Responsibility, should help build the capacity of youths so as to enable them manage this new business model effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: Bank, Beyond-the-branch banking, Financial Institutions, Informal Sector, Unemployment

Introduction

The major recurring decimal in Nigeria's economic and social challenges is the youth unemployment. Youth unemployment in Nigeria, the most populous black nation in the world, has been on the increase for many years. Majority of youths are unable to find gainful employment in spite of their willingness to work. Despite the high number of youths' enrollment in formal education in Nigeria and the turnout of graduates each year, job opportunities to absorb these graduates are few (Akinsola, 2021). Youth unemployment is defined as young adults between the ages of 18 and 35 who are willing to work but unable to secure productive employment (International Labor Organization, 2019). Unemployment occurs when a person who is actively searching for employment is unable to find work. It is a state of not having jobs. Unemployment is one of the developmental problems that face every developing economy in the 21st century. This has become a global concern because of existential threats posed to other developed nations of the world who seem to have gotten it right economically and have a near-zero unemployment rate. For instance, in 2019, the Central Intelligence Agency alerted that Nigeria's bloated population of unemployed youths will have grave consequences for Nigeria, Africa, and the rest of the world if it is not tackled firmly. Olorunfemi (2021) asserted that unemployment has become a big issue for Nigeria's young population. The high percentage of youth unemployment in Nigeria has contributed to the country's poverty and insecurity. The National Bureau of Statistics (2019) puts the population of young people in Nigeria at 80 million, representing 60% of the total population of the country. Sixty-four million of them are unemployed and one million and six hundred thousand (1.6 million) are underemployed. (Opafunso & Omoseni, 2014).

A lot of scholars have posited several factors that caused astronomical rise in youth unemployment in Nigeria and some of them include lack of required skills by prospective employees and overreliance on white-collar jobs as career prospects (Emeh & Eke, 2012). Dike et al. in Akinsola (2021) pointed out that the causes of unemployment are multi-faceted, but criticized Nigerian education system for having a hand in the youth unemployment crisis. The first critique is that young people

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking ... (Olayiwola, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685065>

are only prepared for white-collar employment and not for entrepreneurial, technical, and vocational opportunities as job producers. The second critique is that the education is not tailored to the 21st-century workplace knowledge, skills, and training requirements. However, Jose in Nwagbara, Ugal, and Uyang (2011) argued that unemployment was not an issue in traditional African culture. In traditional African civilization, seventy-five percent of the population was involved in agriculture, while the other twenty-five percent earned a livelihood via minor trade, goldsmithing, blacksmithing, among others.

The Nigerian government, at various levels, has formulated and adopted different policies aimed at tackling the rising youth unemployment in the country through job creation and facilitation of various youth empowerment programmes. Some of these policies birthed the formation of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YOUWIN), Subsidy Re-investment Programme (SURE-P), the NPower programme, and the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) among others (Salami 2013; Olorunfemi, 2021). Although, it has been observed that these efforts have achieved limited success in reducing youth unemployment as evidenced in the prevailing unemployment rates in the country, it is notable that these interventions were aimed at developing both the formal and the informal sector of the economy.

Out of myriads of policies and interventions of the Nigerian government towards stemming the tides of youth unemployment, of essence to this study is the financial inclusion policy introduced by the Central Bank of Nigeria in 2012 to give a broad range easy access of formal financial products and services to the unbanked and underbanked population in Nigeria. Part of the strategies for achieving this policy is the introduction of agent banking service delivery and mobile banking system which are otherwise referred to, in this study, as beyond-the-branch banking. Beyond-the-branch banking is the process of engaging a licensed third-party retail outlets (otherwise known as agents) to conduct customer transactions on behalf of the financial institutions. It is of note that this policy was not directly targeted at reducing youth unemployment in Nigeria but its implementation has brought about job opportunities in the informal sector to the teeming population of Nigerian youths. Unemployment breeds poverty. Therefore, the realization that financial inclusion is pivotal in the fight against poverty and in reaching the goal of inclusive economic development leads to an increased focus on financial inclusion policies and initiatives, and the subsequent introduction of the Point of Sales (POS) service business to the Nigerian economy.

In recent time, there has been a tremendous increase in the population of young people owning or operating the beyond-the-branch banking business. Beyond-the-branch banking retail outlets are common sights everywhere in the urban, suburban and rural Nigeria. For instance, First Bank of Nigeria in 2022 announced that there are over 155,000 of its banking agents (Firstmonie agents) locations in 772 out of 774 local government areas in Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory. Bulk of the owners of these outlets are young demographic. The number of banking agents increased from 83,560 in 2018 to 236,940 in 2019, according to the Central Bank of Nigeria. However, these figures exclude agents who are not covered by Shared Agent Network Expansion Facilities. The implication of this is that beyond-the-branch banking facilitated the employment of 236,940 young Nigerians in 2019 excluding the huge number of direct and indirect employment facilitated by the CBN-licensed Super Agents and mobile money operators like Paga, OPay, PayCentre, PayCom, Baxi among others.

However, relative provision of employment is one, ascertaining whether the employment actually leads to profitability and income stability of the youth demographic is another. It is on this premise that this paper sought to study the impact of beyond-the-branch banking system on youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State. The findings of this study would be greatly beneficial to government and other stakeholders in the banking industry in providing feedbacks on the policy implementation of the beyond-the-branch banking. It would provide feedbacks on the strengths and weaknesses of the policy as touching the youths and employment. This study would equally enlighten the Nigerian youths to look beyond the white-collar jobs and make the most of the opportunity provided by the informal sector of the economy.

Youth unemployment is one of the most challenging economic and social problems facing Nigeria. In fact, it is the trigger to many socio-economic and socio-political challenges bedeviling Nigeria. With the population of 80 million youth, out of which 64 million are unemployed while 1.6 million are underemployed as noted by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria is sitting on a timebomb which when finally detonated would pose a sort of existential threats to the global community. Already, Nigeria has witnessed a high rate of poverty and insecurity which is a direct consequence of youth unemployment.

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking ... (Olayiwola, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685065>

Successive governments have formulated and adopted different policies aimed at tackling the rising youth unemployment in the country through job creation and facilitation of various youth empowerment programmes. But these reforms seem to have achieved limited success in reducing youth unemployment as evidenced by the prevailing unemployment rates in the country. However, with the introduction of the beyond-the-branch banking through the implementation of the financial inclusion policy, there seems to appear another strategy for combating the youth unemployment in Nigeria. It is on this premise that this study intended to investigate the impact of beyond-the-branch banking on youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this study was to determine the impact of beyond-the-branch banking system on youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study sought to determine;

1. the extent to which profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State;
2. whether income stability of beyond-the-branch bankers reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State;
3. the correlation between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study.

1. To what extent does profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?
2. Does income stability of beyond-the-branch bankers reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. Both primary and secondary sources of data collection were employed for the study. Primary data were collected through the administration of questionnaire while secondary data were gathered through related research journals and textbooks. The study was conducted in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 995 beyond-the-branch bankers (including 553 beyond-the-branch bankers that registered with the commercial banks and 442 beyond-the-branch bankers that registered with super agents) in the local government as at year 2023. The sample size for the study was 285 beyond-the-branch bankers. Slovin's formula was used to get the sample size, and simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection and it was validated by two Business Education experts. Pilot study was conducted on the beyond-the-branch bankers outside the target population of the study. The reliability of the data collected from the pilot study was tested using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test and 0.677 reliability level was obtained. Therefore, the reliability of the instrument was considered reliable for the study. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by type of beyond-the-branch banker

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking ... (Olayiwola, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685065>

Table 1: Type of Beyond-the-branch Banker

Type of beyond-the-branch Banker	Frequency	Percent
POS Terminal-Enabled Super-Agent	117	41.1
MoMo Agent	69	24.2
POS Terminal-Enabled Bank Agent	99	34.7
Total	285	100

Table 1 above shows the distribution of types of beyond-the-branch bankers that participated in the study. They include POS Terminal-Enabled Super-Agent 117 (41.1%), MoMo Agent 69 (24.2%) and POS Terminal-Enabled Bank Agent 99 (34.7%).

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender of beyond-the-branch Banker	Frequency	Percent
Female	165	57.9
Male	120	42.1
Total	285	100

Table 2 reveals the gender distribution of the beyond-the-branch bankers who participated in the study. 57.9% of the respondents were female while 42.1% of the respondents were and male.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
M.Sc.	03	1.1
HND/B.Sc.	103	36.1
NCE/OND	157	55.1
O' Level	22	7.7
Total	285	100

Table 3 shows the educational qualification of the respondents. The majority (i.e., 55.1%) of the respondents are NCE/OND holders while O' level, HND/B.Sc., and M.Sc. holders represent 7.7%, 36.1% and 1.1% respectively.

Research Question 1

To what extent does profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation scores on the extent to which profitability of Beyond-The-Branch Banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

S/N	Items	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Beyond-the-branch banking as a lucrative business reduces youth unemployment.	3.08	1.037	Very High
2.	The making of ends meets by beyond-the-bank bankers can assist in reducing youth unemployment.	3.04	.828	Very High
3.	The opportunity to save money from the beyond-the-bank banking to set up other business can reduce youth unemployment.	2.99	1.020	Very High
4.	Reduction in profit making as a result of charges from the principal bank can lead to youth unemployment.	2.43	1.174	Low Extent
5.	Reduction in sales due to competition from other beyond-the-bank bankers can promote youth unemployment.	2.54	1.167	High Extent

Source: Field survey (2023)

From table 4 above, the respondents agreed to a very high extent that the profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment. This is evident by the mean rating of items 1, 2, 3 and 5 which were above the criterion mean weight of 2.50. This implies that to a very high extent, the respondents perceived that the beyond-the-branch banking is a

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking ... (Olayiwola, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685065>

lucrative business and that it reduces youth unemployment. However, the respondents disagreed that the charges from the principal bank could lead to youth unemployment.

Research Question 2

Does income stability of beyond-the-branch bankers reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Table 5: Mean and standard deviation scores on income stability of beyond-the-bank bankers and reduction in youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Because I can predict my sales volume per day, Beyond-the-branch banking reduces youth unemployment.	2.79	.998	Agreed
2.	I make regular profits from the beyond-the-bank operation; therefore, it reduces youth unemployment.	2.95	1.086	Agreed
3.	Beyond-the-branch banking enables me to have a stable source of income; therefore, it reduces youth unemployment.	3.02	.985	Agreed
4.	I would need more capital to maintain a higher level of income in order to benefit from the employment opportunity provided by the beyond-the-branch banking.	3.10	1.087	Agreed
5.	Beyond-the-branch banking enables me to meet my immediate financial needs; therefore, it reduces youth unemployment.	2.72	1.155	Agreed

Source: Field survey (2023)

Table 5 revealed that the ability of the beyond-the-branch bankers to relatively predict their sales volume per day, make regular profits and meet their immediate financial needs lead to their income stability and consequently reduce youth unemployment. On the other hand, the higher the working capital or float to meet customers' needs the higher the level of income and profitability of the business.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Table 6: The relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

	N	t	df	sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	St. Deviation
Relationship	285	54.824	99	.000	8.07	1.472

Source: Field survey (2023)

Data in table 6 indicated that there is a positive relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment. The calculated alpha level of 0.000 is less than the significant level of 0.05 hence, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one in table 4 indicates that the lucrativeness of the beyond-the-branch banking, ability of the beyond-the-branch bankers to make ends meet, opportunity to save money from the beyond-the-branch banking to set up other businesses and low transaction charges are some of the indicators that rate the extent to which profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment. This is in line with the position of Mohamad, Suraidi, Rahman and Suhaimi (2016) that agency banking is a lucrative option for the unemployed. Akintoye (2018) equally posited that quite a number of young Nigerians are no longer fixated on the non-existent white-collar jobs but have now sought comfort in the opportunity

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking ... (Olayiwola, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685065>

provided by the informal sector through the beyond-the-branch banking. Beyond-the-branch banking has created more employment opportunities in the informal sector with the same vigor with which the introduction of the mobile telecommunications networks otherwise known as the Global System for Mobile communication (GSM) generated employment for the teeming Nigerians. Macjohn (2022) reported that the total amount of transactions at POS terminals in year 2021 in Nigeria hit ₦4.1 trillion. The reason for the huge transaction is that banks in Nigeria only open their branches in busy areas, where there are markets or many other businesses. People living far from the bank are often stranded and resort to patronizing the POS business thereby resulting in huge profitability for the operators.

Results in table 5 shows that the ability of the beyond-the-bank bankers to relatively predict their sales volume per day, make regular profits and meet their immediate financial needs lead to their income stability and consequently reduce youth unemployment. The income of a business is considered to be stable if its earnings from work or capital does not suffer more than 25% variation over the period of a year. This is in tandem with the proposition of Omoseni and Opafunso (2014) that a stable business by income is one whose owner is able to track expenses, forecast sales volume, maintain a positive budget and leverage on opportunity for growth. The findings also revealed that the higher the working capital or float to meet customers' needs the higher the level of income and profitability of the business.

Conclusion

This paper concludes that despite the prevailing rate of youth unemployment in the country, quite a number of young Nigerians have availed themselves of the opportunities provided by the informal sector through the beyond-the-branch banking to mitigate the challenges. The extent to which the profitability and the income stability of the beyond-the-branch bankers reduce unemployment among the youths is significantly high. It afforded the youth the opportunity to make regular profits, make ends meet, have a stable source of income and save money to set up other businesses. Whereas the policy of beyond-the-branch banking was not directly targeted at reducing youth unemployment, its implementation has brought about job opportunities in the informal sector to the teeming population of Nigerian youths. However, the major challenges incapacitating young Nigerians from making the most of these opportunities include but not limited to shortage of working capital/float requirement and security risks.

Recommendations

Stemming from the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made, that;

1. government should assist in the provision of adequate physical and cyber security;
2. the Central Bank of Nigeria should also provide or facilitate loans specifically for youths venturing into the beyond-the-branch banking so as to provide them with sufficient working capital;
3. Banks and other financial institutions, as a form of Corporate Social Responsibility, should help build the capacity of youths so as to enable them manage this new business model effectively and efficiently;
4. Nigerian youths should look beyond the formal sector and avail themselves of opportunities provided by the informal sectors.

References

- Akinsola, O. O. (2021). *Reducing youths unemployment in Nigeria: The development of a technical and vocational education and training survey instrument*. PhD Dissertation. University of Tennessee. https://trace.tennessee.edu/utk_graddiss/6627
- Akintoye, I. R. (2018). Reducing unemployment through the informal sector: A case study of Nigeria. *European Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 11, 97-106.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (2013). *Guidelines for the Regulation of Agent Banking and Agent Banking Relationships in Nigeria*. Banking and Payment System Department.
- Eke, J. & Emeh, I. (2012). Tackling youth unemployment in Nigeria: The Lagos State development and empowerment programmes initiatives. *Afro-Asian Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(34), 22-29.
- International Labour Organization (2019). *World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends*. PRODOC. Geneva.
- Macjohn, S. (2022). *Is POS Business in Nigeria Profitable? The FinTech Africa*. <https://thefintechafrika.com/business/is-pos-business-in-nigeria-profitable-what-you-need-to-know-before-you-start/> Accessed on 25th July, 2022
- Mohamad, S. J., Suraidi, N. N., Rahman, N. N. S. & Suhaimi, R. D. S. (2016). A Study on relationship between inventory management and company performance: A case study of textile chain store. *Journal of Advanced Management Science*,

Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking ... (Olayiwola, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685065>

4(4), 299-304.

- Nwagbara, E. N., Ugal, G. A., & Uyang, F. A. (2011). Youth unemployment and its consequences in Calabar metropolis: Need for government intervention. *Global Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(1&2), 75–82.
- Olorunfemi, G. C. (2021). Addressing the state of youth unemployment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology and Social Development*, 9(4), 102–113.
- Omoseni, O. A. & Opafunso, Z. O., (2014). The impact of small and medium scale enterprises on economic development of Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, 5(16), 115–123.
- Salami C. G. E. (2013). Youth unemployment in Nigeria: A time for creative intervention. *International Journal of Business and Marketing Management*, 1(2), 18-26.